

Urban Food Policy: Evolution over Time from Milano Expo 2015

*An Analysis of Urban Food Policy in the Milan Urban Food
Policy Pact Framework*

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Urban Food Policy

Urban Food Policies versus Food Policies

Food policy refers to government influence on food production and distribution, addressing a set of concerns such as food safety, quality, production, distribution, consumption, and cultural aspects (Chatzopoulou, 2019). These policies operate across various levels of governance, sectors, and actors. They broadly include actions and decisions regarding food production, and its impact on public health, the environment, and natural resources (Lang et al., 2009).

Food policy is a type of governmental strategy and regulation policy that has the general aim to shape the food system and to ensure food security and adequate nutrition. It includes various government actions impacting food supply, price, production, distribution, quality, and safety (Hawkes & Halliday, 2017). Recent approaches to food policy, influenced by concepts such as food security, food safety, and food sovereignty, aim for comprehensive solutions, including all aspects of the food system. This multidisciplinary and multisectoral approach addresses social, political, economic, and environmental factors (Hawkes & Halliday, 2017). Contrary to focusing solely on production, food policy emphasises fair production and consumption, offering insights into what is produced and consumed, and the equity of distribution (Lang et al., 2009).

The concept of food policy has a historical presence, even if under different names. It gained recognition as a crucial state policy objective, particularly in World War II, addressing national security and societal needs during famine periods.

Post-World War II, optimising food and agricultural production became important for achieving food security (Shaw, 2007). Maxwell & Slater (2004) made an important difference between “old” (1970s) and “new” (2000s) food policy eras, signifying changes in food policy dynamics. Lang & Barling (2012) identified four primary phases shaping food policy evolution. The initial phase (1940-1950) emphasised agricultural production. Subsequently, the 1970s focused on food markets and development policy. The era between 1980 and 2000 highlighted environmental crises and market failures. Finally, the 21st century struggles with food policy connected with public health challenges.

Food policy is an instrument of market regulation, designed and implemented to solve the problems of market failures (i.e., externalities, asymmetric information). The regulative

framework of food policy is usually national or supranational (e.g., the European Union is an authority beyond nation-states, addressing complex problems that single states would not be able to manage on their own). In contrast, in the last decade, Urban Food Policies (UFPs) have been implemented, aiming to address specific problems at a local level (Banterle & Zeneli, 2025a).

UFPs involve coordinated efforts by city governments to address food-related issues. While these policies often involve civil society and various actors, actions led solely by citizens without government involvement do not constitute official UFPs. These policies range from comprehensive approaches addressing multiple challenges across the food system, to targeted actions tackling specific issues like food insecurity or food waste (Bricas et al., 2017). Moreover, introducing sustainability principles in these policies can help cities create more resilient and equitable food systems (Banterle & Zeneli, 2025b). Integrated UFPs require collaboration among different government departments and the establishment of new governance bodies. However, UFPs, in their current forms, serve as one element in broader food system changes and operate within the constraints of multi-level governance. Cities have limited authority and varying capacities to address food problems within their borders, as many issues are interconnected with national and global policies like trade, economy, agriculture, and public health.

UFPs' types

An urban food system is considered effective if it is integrated with sustainable urban development and land planning regulations. To achieve this at a city level, the local government can adopt 4 types of UFPs. UFPs are not only regulative, since at the local level, there are not only problems raised from market failures, but also problems in terms of equity.

Figure 1 displays the UFPs' categorisation, and a brief description of each type is provided as follows.

Fig. 1. UFPs classification. Source: Authors' elaboration.

Substantive policies. Substantive policies involve direct interventions by local governmental authorities to address local needs by managing the existing services or activating new ones. In the context of food policies, substantive approaches often focus on enhancing public services in places - such as school and hospital cafeterias - or establishing logistical infrastructures - such as food hubs or retail markets. Substantive food policies may be: (i) demonstrative - referring to the public actor organising a pilot activity to inspire others to replicate it (i.e., urban agriculture pilot projects in Detroit, transforming blighted municipal land into urban farms, and the Blizkata ferma in Bulgaria that uses the regenerative agriculture), and (ii) executing - involving the direct offering and implementation of the service by the public actor for citizens' use (i.e., public food hubs and farmers' market in Toronto).

Regulative policies. Regulative policies impose behavioural restrictions on individuals and groups, involving the government and establishing general rules of behaviour, dictating actions that must or must not be taken. In the context of food policies, these regulations

may ensure the quality of services or products provided to consumers. Food regulation policies can be categorised as: (i) binding - when they compel action (i.e. zoning regulation in Seattle that designs specific areas for city agricultural use), (ii) banning - when they forbid action (i.e., limiting fast food outlets near schools in promoting land use for healthier food options in South LA; setting the minimum of 90% for organic food served in institutional canteens in Copenhagen, Denmark), or (iii) allowing - when they permit action (i.e. the altered land use regulation in Paris allows rooftop beekeeping in Paris).

Fiscal policies. Fiscal policy may involve the introduction of specific taxes or incentives on food production and trade in urban areas. This intervention either encourages or taxes certain behaviours, acting as a selective driver of favourable practices. Fiscal policies can be categorised as: (i) incentivising - when they promote economic practices (i.e., San Francisco property tax reduction for a private landowner to food production land allocation under the Urban Agriculture Incentive Zones Act; Paris, France, co-founded local farmers' markets with logistics to connect peri-urban farms with schools), and (ii) taxing - when they restrict or penalise through economic measures (i.e. Philadelphia's soda tax collected funds are used for urban gardens and fresh food markets in underserved areas).

Informative policies. An informative policy carried out via educational initiatives and campaigns has the potential to trigger widespread impacts. In many food policies, this approach often involves establishing advisory and advocacy groups, such as "food policy councils", including various stakeholders. Informative food policies can be characterised as: (i) empowering - when supporting civic engagement and awareness-building (i.e. The New York City Food Policy Council engages diverse stakeholders to address sustainable urban development; "Thursday Veggie Day" in Ghent, Belgium, motivates the citizens to adopt one meat-free day per week), or (ii) educational - when introducing initiatives for future generations (i.e., The Edible Schoolyard Project in Berkeley, California, a school garden programs to teach students about sustainable food systems and healthy eating habits).

Milan Urban Food Policy Pact

The Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP) is an international pact with the main objective of developing sustainable, inclusive, resilient, safe, and diverse food systems to ensure healthy and accessible food for all, while minimising waste and conserving biodiversity at the urban level. It was introduced by the city of Milan in 2015 during Expo

Milano, and since then, it has been signed by over 200 cities around the world. It is a continuous-time initiative (i.e., an annual Milan Pact Award ceremony is held). The year 2016 was the first year the ceremony awarded the best practices. The year 2021, due to COVID-19 restrictions, was the first year to put on hold the ceremony. The year 2023 was the first year of the Milan Pact Awards Retreat, an event aiming to share the best practices among previous winners. Again, for the year 2024 was not held a ceremony, while in 2025, the ceremony is planned to be held during the MUFPP Global Forum in Milan on October 15, 2025. Behind this event stand the City of Milan and the Cariplo Foundation, intending to recognise the most creative efforts and monitor which cities were implementing the commitments they had made when they joined the pact (MUFPP, 2025). The main objectives of the MUFPP are to:

- (i) foster the development of sustainable food systems;
- (ii) improve nutrition and food accessibility;
- (iii) reduce food waste;
- (iv) promote food education and healthy diets;
- (v) strengthen food production and distribution within the urban setting.

The Pact encourages cities to work on several key areas:

- *Governance* - Developing multi-level governance systems to support the integration of food policy;
- *Social and economic equity* - Ensuring food policies are inclusive and equitable;
- *Sustainable diets and nutrition* - Promoting access to food and healthy diets for all;
- *Food production* - Encouraging sustainable food production and processing;
- *Food supply and distribution* - Supporting fair and sustainable food distribution systems;
- *Food waste* - Reducing food waste through effective management strategies.

Although the six thematic areas of the Pact provide a comprehensive framework for urban food action, it must be stressed that the initiatives and projects developed within these domains cannot be directly mapped onto the typology presented in Figure 1. Indeed, a single initiative under one specific area of the Pact may include multiple types of UFPs, combining, for example, regulatory provisions, fiscal instruments, and informative measures within a single intervention. This fact calls for the necessity of adopting a case-specific analytical approach to set explicit linkages between the initiatives promoted under the Pact and the categories of UFPs identified in the classification. Such an approach allows for a

more precise and context-sensitive understanding of how UFPs are operationalised in practice.

Any city can join the pact, and this is translated into a commitment to develop integrated food policies, sharing best practices, and participating in a global network for UFPs development. The pact itself provides a framework for action but allows cities the flexibility to develop initiatives that address their specific contexts and challenges. The pact has inspired various initiatives, such as urban agriculture projects, school feeding programs, and improvements in food waste management. The ongoing commitment and expansion of the pact will be crucial in achieving its objectives and creating more sustainable urban food landscapes worldwide.

Urban Food Policy - geographical analysis

To understand the descriptive analysis provided below, there is a need to define some utilised terms. Adherent cities are the cities that have already signed the pact (they may or may not have yet implemented an Urban Food Policy - UFP). The concept cities that implemented UFPs are used specifically to identify those adherent cities that have already implemented any UFP. The period of data includes 2016-2022 (except the year 2021 with no data).

World

On a global scale, there are more than 200 cities that have signed the MUFPP since 2015. The number of UFPs implemented by European cities, for the whole period 2016-2022, is 246, followed by Central and Latin America with 114 UFPs implemented. Africa is the third continent that has implemented in total of 87 UFPs, followed by North America with 78 UFPs, Asia with 69 UFPs, the Middle East with 14 UFPs, and Australia with 3 UFPs, for a total of 611 implemented UFPs during the period 2016-2022 (Figure 2a).

Fig. 2a. World - UFPs aggregate distribution among continents, for the period 2016-2022.
Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

In Figure 2b is represented the distribution among different categories of UFPs, for each continent, for the whole period 2016-2022. As one can see it, in Europe is more dominant governance and social and economic equity UFPs, followed by sustainable diet and nutrition and food supply and distribution. In Central and Latin America, the governance, sustainable diet and nutrition, and food production are leading. In Africa prevails the food production UFPs followed by governance and sustainable diet and nutrition. Sustainable diet and nutrition, food production and governance UFPs are prevalent in North America. In Asia, prevail governance, social and economic equity UFPs, and sustainable diet and nutrition. The Middle East and Australia focus is in social and economic equity UFPs.

This distribution reveals the heterogeneity in priorities among continents, reflecting their different context in shaping their specific urban realities and problems. Europe remains the leader in the number and variety of implemented UFPs for the period 2016-2022.

Fig. 2b. World - UFPs distribution among continents and categories, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

In Figure 2c, there is a graphical analysis over time of the number of initiatives, adherent cities and respective countries.

Fig. 2c. World - distribution over time of initiatives, number of adherent cities and respective countries, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

The number of implemented UFPs has an increasing trend (except for the year 2018), while the number of adherent cities is oscillating in cycles, and the number of respective countries has a relatively increasing trend, reflecting the participation of cities from new countries rather than new cities from the existing countries. The number of implemented initiatives is more than the number of respective cities, suggesting that an adherent city may implement more than one UFP.

In Figure 2d, there are presented adherent cities that have implemented UFPs (one or more). For clarity, the map below includes the global distribution of UFPs for the whole period of study, 2016-2022 (there is no certain information that every single policy was continuously active from 2016).

Fig. 2d. Adherent cities in MUFPP with implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration in Google My Maps.

In 2016, the most implemented UFP among cities was related to the governance category, followed by the social and economic equity, and food supply and distribution (Figure 2e), from a total of 53 initiatives. In 2022, the image is different. The number is 5 times higher (around 251 initiatives), and sustainable diet and nutrition are the prevalent UFPs, followed by governance and food production. The trend is following the global agenda of sustainability, food production for an increasing demographic trend, governance, as the needed legal and regulatory framework for the new UFPs, and big structural changes in the global economy (e.g., Russia-Ukraine conflict, Covid-19 pandemic, etc.).

Fig. 2e. World - Evolution over time of implemented UFPs among adherent cities in MUFPP, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

Europe

The trend over time in the number of adherent cities that have implemented one or more UFPs is shown in Figure 3a.

Fig. 3a. Europe - Evolution over time of the number of adherent cities which implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

In 2022, the number of European adherent cities that implemented UFPs was 5 times higher compared to the year 2016. In Figure 3b, the trend over time of different types of UFPs implemented is displayed.

Fig. 3b. Europe - Total number of implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

For the first two years, governance was the prevalent UFP, followed by social and economic equity, while in 2022, sustainable diet and nutrition took the first place, putting governance and social and economic equity respectively in the second and third place.

The map below (Figure 3c) shows the distribution of implemented UFPs in the framework of MUFPP for Europe.

Fig. 3c. Europe - Prevalent UFPs among adherent cities in MUFPP, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

Governance, and social and economic equity UFPs are more distributed among cities in Spain, the UK, and Northern Italy, while cities in Portugal, Southern Spain, Eastern Germany, and Northern UK are implementing policies focused on sustainable diets and nutrition. Cities in Ireland, Western France, and Denmark focus more on food production, while in cities in Italy, Spain, Belgium, and France, there is a significant implementation of policies concerning food supply and distribution. Concentrated mostly in cities in Belgium, Switzerland, Italy, and Albania, there are initiatives on food waste.

This geographical distribution highlights the diversity of approaches within the pact, showing how different European urban areas can contribute to the broader goals of the MUFPP based on their unique contexts.

Some European best practices

- 1- “From food waste to healthy, off-season food” - Riga, Latvia (a special mention from Milan Pact Awards 2016, **Food Waste** category). It was a project oriented to the conversion of methane emissions from the country’s largest landfill to the country’s largest source of green energy, to heat greenhouse production of fresh vegetables in winter.
- 2- “Organic Conversion Project” - Copenhagen, Denmark (a special mention from Milan Pact Awards 2017, **Sustainable Diet and Nutrition** category). It has succeeded in reaching a 90% organic food procurement target for all 900 municipal kitchens.
- 3- “Food waste reduction” programme - London, UK (a winner on Milan Pact Awards 2022, **Food Waste** category). It was an initiative offering interventions and evidence-based policies to reduce consumption-based emissions from food and to implement pioneering circular food system solutions.

Central and Latin America

The trend over time of the adherent cities number which implemented one or more UFPs in Central and Latin America is represented in Figure 4a.

Fig. 4a. Central and Latin America - Evolution over time of the number of adherent cities which implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

Except for the year 2013, the trend of Central and Latin America adherent cities which are implementing UFPs is increasing. 3 times more adherent cities which implemented UFPs are registered in the year 2022 compared to the year 2016.

The bar chart in Figure 4b presents the evolution over time of UFPs in Central and Latin America from 2016. Governance and food production were prevalent back in 2016, while in 2022, sustainable diet and nutrition UFPs were leading with 12 initiatives implemented.

The governance policies were prevalent in the beginning (setting standards, regulations, and policies to better control food safety, distribution, and sustainable practices), but in 2022, sustainable diet and nutrition UFPs-type became prevalent,

reflecting a growing regional concern with public health issues, such as malnutrition and obesity. After the COVID-19 pandemic, the renewed focus on sustainable diet and nutrition alongside governance reflects a holistic approach to recovery.

Fig. 4b. Central and Latin America - Total number of implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration in Google My Maps.

The map below (Figure 4c) displays visually the distribution of the prevalent UFPs for Central and Latin America. From Central America, cities from Guatemala are focusing on sustainable diet and nutrition and food supply and distribution UFPs-type, while cities from Costa Rica focus on practices related to food production and governance. The emphasis on food supply and distribution indicates efforts to streamline the pathway from farm to table, which can help reduce food losses and ensure that fresh, affordable food is accessible across the city, particularly important in urban settings where logistical challenges and food deserts can limit access to essential food resources.

The participation of these cities in the MUFPP not only demonstrates their commitment to improving their urban food systems but also positions them as regional leaders in the global movement towards sustainable urban development.

Fig. 4c. Central and Latin America - Prevalent UFPs among adherent cities in MUFPP, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration in Google My Maps.

From Latin America, cities from Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador, and Peru adhere to MUFPP. All big cities are committed to implement all UFP types. Medellin city in Colombia is worth to be mentioned since has implemented all of UFPs, while Brazil is the leader in the region, implementing all the UFPs-type, with the highest number of all the countries in the region (49 out of 114), distributed in Araraquara, Belo Horizonte, Curitiba, Porto Alegre, Recife, Rio de Janeiro, and São Paulo city.

This widespread participation and varied focus demonstrate Latin America's proactive approach to tackling urban food system challenges through the MUFPP.

Some Central and Latin American best practices

- 1- "Lima Sostenibile, promoviendo la seguridad alimentaria" - Lima, Peru (winner in Milan Pact Awards 2018, **Food Production** category). It aimed to promote food security and local food production in the city through measures that encourage a self-sustaining economy that is resilient to climate change.
- 2- "Hortas Cariocas" programme on urban agriculture - Rio de Janeiro, Brazil (special mention in Milan Pact Awards 2019, **Food Production** category). Its focus was the development of urban agroecology, providing access to poor communities with nutritious food and job opportunities.
- 3- "Agro-ecological food production" - Rosario, Argentina (winner of Milan Pact Awards 2022, **Food Production** category). It was a project that improved resilience and adaptation to climate change with green infrastructure, integrating recreational and productive spaces into urban planning.

Africa

The trend over time of the adherent African cities (which implemented one or more UFPs) number is represented in Figure 5a.

Fig. 5a. Africa - Evolution over time of the number of adherent cities which implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

In 2016, the adherence of African cities was modest, with only four cities, while in 2022, this number is 5 times higher, demonstrating an increasing interest of African cities to be part of big agendas related to food and sustainability.

The bar chart in Figure 5b illustrates the total number of UFPs implemented in Africa from 2016 to 2022 across different focus areas, with the note that there was no implementation in 2021 due to the COVID-19 emergency.

Fig. 5b. Africa - Total number of implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

In 2016, although with a modest number of UFPs (only 5), African cities adhered to and covered all the UFP types except food waste. The increase in the number of UFPs during 2022 (35 in total), with the prevalence of food production and sustainable diet and nutrition, suggests a shift towards the most prevalent food-related issues in the African continent.

The map (Figure 5c) provides a graphical representation of the implementation of various UFPs in the framework of MUFPP across different African countries, categorised by specific policy focuses.

Cities, especially in Southern Africa (e.g., Niger, Chad), are prioritising food production. This focus typically involves supporting agricultural productivity, sustainable farming practices, and possibly urban agriculture initiatives to boost local food production. Cities in Somalia and Zambia are concentrating on promoting sustainable diets and nutrition, while cities in Senegal are implementing social and economic equity policies. Governance is the focus of cities in Cameroon and Tunisia, food supply and distribution initiatives are implemented in cities in Namibia and Burkina Faso, while cities in countries like Tanzania and Ghana are focused on policies that address food waste.

Fig. 5c. Africa - Prevalent UFPs among adherent cities in MUFPP, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

Some African best practices

- 1- “Micro gardens in the City of Dakar” - Dakar, Senegal (special mention in Milan Pact Awards 2017, **Food Production** category). It was a plan of action working towards reducing Dakar’s food scarcity using micro gardens in soilless horticultural production, in small urban spaces such as roofs and yards.
- 2- “Urban Early Warning Initiative” - Nairobi, Kenya (special mention in Milan Pact Awards 2019, **Social and Economic Equity** category). It consisted of developing early warning systems and early action responses to crises that affect the poor people living in urban slums.
- 3- School feeding program - Addis Ababa, Ethiopia (winner of Milan Pact Awards 2022, **Sustainable Diets and Nutrition** category). It consisted of a large-scale school feeding programme supported by a sustainable government budget line.

North America

Figure 6a represents the trend over time of adherent cities of North America that have implemented UFPs.

Fig. 6a. North America - Evolution over time of the number of adherent cities which implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

An oscillating trend is noted, with the peak in 2022, reflecting the increasing understanding of North American cities in adhering to such a global initiative as MUFPP, registering a triple of cities in 2022, compared to the year of 2016. Still, compared to the number of European adherent cities or even those of African or Central and Latin America, the number of North American adherent cities is the lowest. All the initiatives are concentrated in 16 cities.

Figure 6b gives the evolution over time of the number of UFPs implemented in North America. There is a consistent, though oscillating, focus on sustainable diet and nutrition initiatives (since 20216), reflecting one of the main demographic issues that North American

cities are dealing with: obesity. In 2022, an interesting fact was observed: food production initiatives are prioritised, reflecting the possible supply chain disruptions during COVID-19, and concerns over the food security of the population in times of crises.

Fig. 6b. North America - Total number of implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022.
Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration in Google My Maps.

Among the cities of the Northern American countries which have adhered to MUFPP (Figure 6c), Los Angeles and New York City (USA), Vancouver (Canada) and Mérida (Mexico) focus on governance, indicating robust efforts in creating and enforcing policies that regulate and support sustainable food systems. Toronto (Canada) and Washington D.C. (USA) are investing more in sustainable diet and nutrition UFPs-type, reflecting initiatives aimed at addressing diet-related health issues such as diabetes and heart disease. An interesting fact from Canada is that cities that share the border with the USA are the ones adhering to MUFPP and following similar trends with them, reflecting their dependency also in terms of UFPs choice. From Mexico, two interesting cases are brought: (1) the case of Guadalajara city focusing on food supply and distribution, food production, sustainable diet and nutrition, and food waste, and addressing in this way, both, the front and end stages of the food system lifecycle; and (2) the case of Pachuca city, with the sole focus on food

production suggesting that it is in the early stages of developing its urban food policy and has chosen to prioritise boosting local food production as a foundational step towards broader food system improvements.

Fig. 6c. North America - Prevalent UFPs among adherent cities in MUFPP, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration in Google My Maps.

Some North American best practices

- 1- “Community Food Works for Newcomers: food as a tool for settlement and integration” - Toronto, Canada (winner of Milan Pact Awards 2017, **Social and Economic Equity** category). It was a program that used food as the instrument to create opportunities for social inclusion and engagement, to facilitate resettlement and integration into Canadian life.
- 2- “Food as medicine” - Washington D.C., USA (winner in Milan Pact Awards 2019, **Sustainable Diet and Nutrition** category); It consisted of a wide spectrum of programs and services that respond to the critical link between nutrition and chronic illness.
- 3- “A New York City Framework for Good Food Purchasing”, New York, USA (winner in Milan Pact Awards 2022, **Governance** category). It consisted of a food procurement system to serve more than 230 million meals annually to the city’s most vulnerable populations.

Asia

The trend over time of the number of Asian adherent cities that have implemented UFPs is represented in Figure 7a. The trend has been increasing since 2018, with 7 times more cities in 2022 compared to the year 2016 (respectively 21 versus 3). The interesting fact for the year 2022 was that 10 out of 21 adherent cities which implemented one or more UFPs were from India, indicating a spatial concentration (India as a leading actor within the region).

Fig. 7a. Asia - Evolution over time of the number of adherent cities which implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

Considering all the types of MUFPP food policies, for Asian cities was possible starting from 2019, with the visible increased attention during 2022, where the priority was given to governance and food waste, social and economic equity, sustainable diet and nutrition, food production and food supply distribution in this order (Figure 7b).

Fig. 7b. Asia - Total number of implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

The map below (Figure 7c) shows the prevalent implemented UFPs among Asian cities adherent to MUFPP. Cities in South Korea and India are among those that prioritise the sustainable diet and nutrition UFPs-type. This could reflect efforts to integrate more locally sourced, less environmentally damaging food sources into urban diets, possibly driven by concerns about obesity, food security, or environmental impact. The focus on food waste in cities in Turkey, India, and Indonesia is significant. It indicates a prioritisation of reducing food loss and waste in the supply chain, which is crucial for these populous countries where food security is a persistent challenge.

Fig. 7c. Asia - Prevalent UFPs among adherent cities in MUFPF, for the period 2016-2022.
 Source. Data from the MUFPF website, authors elaboration.

South Korea and China’s cities focus on improving food supply and distribution systems, while Indian cities’ prioritisation of food governance likely reflects a comprehensive approach to managing the food system. With one of the largest populations in the world and rapid urbanisation, effective governance is crucial for India to manage its food systems sustainably and ensure equitable access to food resources.

Some Asian best practices

- 1- “Wanju Localfood No1. Project (WLOP)” - Wanju, South Korea (special mention in Milan Pact Awards 2018, **Food Production** category). It was a pioneering local food initiative, focused on promoting sustainable agriculture by building strong relationships between local producers and consumers.
- 2- “Women Producer’s Markets” - Mezitli, Turkey (winner in Milan Pact Awards 2019, **Social and Economic Equity** category). It was a program that helped to strengthen local women as sellers by providing them with space and support to sell their local products.
- 3- “E-Cool Mandi” - Rourkela, India (winner in Milan Pact Awards 2022, **Social and Economic Equity** category). It consisted of a decentralised cold room run by women, preventing vendor distress and reducing food waste.

Middle East

A modest adherence of Middle East cities can be observed in Figure 8a, with the highest participation in 2016 (3 adherent cities which implemented UFPs: Dubai in the United Arab Emirates, Hebron in the West Bank, and Tel Aviv in Israel). The limited number can be due to slower growth, due to limited institutional capacity or political instability of the region.

Fig. 8a. Middle East - Evolution over time of the number of adherent cities which implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

In Figure 8b it can be observed the distribution over time among different UFP types in the Middle East region. From the start (years 2016 and 2017), the social and economic equity was the focus, alternating later, with the same weight, with sustainable diets and nutrition, governance and food waste UFPs.

Fig. 8b. Middle East - Total number of implemented UFPs, for the period 2016-2022.

Source. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration.

Tel Aviv, Kfar Saba, Herzliya (Israel), Dubai (United Arab Emirates), and Hebron (West Bank - Gaza Strip) are among the cities that adhere to MUFPP, from the Middle East region (Figure 8c). Governance is the focus of the city of Dubai. Dubai’s emphasis on governance suggests a structured approach to managing its food systems, involving the development and enforcement of policies that ensure food safety, quality, and sustainability, indicative of Dubai’s advanced administrative capabilities and its goal to become a leading sustainable and smart city. Food supply and distribution is the policy implemented in the West Bank (along with food waste and social and economic equity), crucial in a region often facing access issues due to political and geographical constraints. Cities in Israel are mainly focused on social and economic equity, reflecting efforts to address disparities in food access and promote inclusive growth within urban settings. This aligns with broader social policies aimed at improving living conditions and reducing inequalities.

Fig. 8c. Middle East - Prevalent UFPs among adherent cities in MUFPP, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration in Google My Maps.

Some Middle East best practices

- 1- “Food Import and Re-Export System” - Dubai, UAE (participating in Milan Pact Awards 2016, **Governance** category). The program consisted of the implementation of an electronic platform to facilitate the food products registration for the companies.
- 2- “Awareness & solid waste disposal”, Hebron, West Bank - Gaza Strip (participating in Milan Pact Awards 2016, **Food Waste** category). It was a program aimed at transitioning from open dumpsites to a modern, sanitary landfill, funded by international donors.
- 3- “Green Eurovision” - Tel Aviv, Israel (special mention in Milan Pact Awards 2019, **Food Waste** category). It was a program aimed to find solutions to the environmental impacts of food festivals, offering a guideline for running sustainable large-scale city events in the future.

Australia

Figure 9 presents the two cities, Sydney and Melbourne, that adhere to MUFPP, focused on food waste and social and economic equity UFPs-type. In total, there are only three practices implemented in 2022. This relatively low level of engagement suggests that either urban food policy might not be a major focus area across Australian cities or that existing policies and frameworks might already be addressing these concerns effectively. Indeed, the UFPs implemented are related to social and economic equity and food waste in two main cities, Melbourne and Sydney. The emphasis on food waste in both cities highlights a commitment to addressing sustainability in urban environments, a focus particularly relevant given the global push towards reducing food waste to address climate change, improve food security, and reduce landfill use. The attention to social and economic equity issues through UFPs underlines efforts to ensure fair access to food resources, which can contribute to tackling poverty, reducing inequality, and promoting social cohesion within urban communities.

Fig. 9. Australia - Prevalent UFPs among adherent cities in MUFPP, for the period 2016-2022. Source. Data from the MUFPP website, authors elaboration in Google My Maps.

Some Australian best practices

- 1- “Community food relief” - Melbourne, Victoria (special mention in Milan Pact Awards 2022, **Social and Economic Equity** category). This program aimed to improve access to food assistance services and support community food growing.
- 2- “Love Food Sydney” - Sydney, New South Wales (participant in Milan Pact Awards 2022, **Food Waste** category). This program consisted of providing training and resources to help businesses and communities reduce the amount of food that goes to landfill.
- 3- “FoodLab” - Sydney, New South Wales (participant in Milan Pact Awards 2022, **Social and Economic Equity** category). This program aimed to empower diverse food entrepreneurs and support a more equitable and sustainable food system.

Conclusion

The analysis of Urban Food Policies (UFPs) in cities across the globe, as an instrument to deal with city-specific problems (Banterle & Zeneli, 2025a), reveals significant advancements in the ways urban areas are addressing food system sustainability and equity. The review of various implementations has highlighted innovative strategies that cities are adopting to address food-related challenges, which include enhancing local food production, reducing food waste, and ensuring equitable food access.

One of the most important findings from the analysis is the heterogeneity among continents: the data show that different continents emphasise specific types of UFPs, reflecting regional socioeconomic, political, and environmental contexts. Europe is a frontrunner, leading both in the number and the variety of UFPs implemented, with a strong emphasis on governance and social equity. This suggests that European cities are not only investing in food systems but also introducing them in broader governance and inclusion frameworks. Africa's emphasis on food production reflects the pressing needs for food security and resilience against scarcity. Central and Latin America's balance between governance, sustainable diets, and production indicates a dual effort to address, on one side, malnutrition and, on the other side, to strengthen food systems through institutional coordination. North America shares a mixed UFPs adaptation, reflecting its multidimensional approach, with governance, diet, and production being equally relevant. Asia's focus on governance and equity highlights the importance of institutional capacity and inclusiveness in highly urbanised and diverse contexts. The Middle East and Australia's focus on social and economic equity suggests that addressing access, fairness, and social inclusion is the priority in their urban food agendas.

The heterogeneous distribution tells us that no single UFP dimension dominates globally; instead, cities tailor their strategies to their specific vulnerabilities and priorities (food insecurity in Africa, governance capacity in Europe and Asia, social and economic equity in the Middle East and Australia).

The analysis confirms that UFPs implementation is highly context-dependent. While Europe remains the leader in both scope and diversity, other continents prioritise dimensions most relevant to their socioeconomic challenges. This heterogeneity confirms the adaptability of UFPs to local urban realities while also underlining the global importance of governance, equity, and sustainability in shaping resilient food systems.

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